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The potential of Living Labs and Land-Based Labs in the arid prairies of Monti Prenestini

liminal_{shape} rural futures

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1.1 Summary of the Action-Research¹

Transitioning a Landscape addressed one of the most pressing challenges for marginal Italian territories: the abandonment of traditional land management practices without the emergence of dynamics capable of sustainably balancing new social, economic and ecological needs. In Monti Prenestini, the project explored whether the *territorial lab*² model can act as a catalyst to trigger these dynamics, promoting new models of active land management and thus preserving the historical and cultural continuity that has characterized these territories in Italy.

The *territorial lab* is inspired by the *Living Lab*³ and *Land-Based Lab*⁴ models, but is distinguished by its focus on the social and relational dynamics that can trigger regeneration processes, rather than on a single technical or scientific objective. At the core of the model is the development of production chains based on niche products rooted in the territory, capable of enhancing local resources and attracting new actors interested in investing in Monti Prenestini.

This approach was developed by integrating scientific research, spatial mapping, and direct involvement of local stakeholders. The project has produced concrete results, including 18 detailed spatial maps, 12 case studies from international *Land-Based Labs* and *Living Labs*, a structured SWOT analysis, and tables ranking the causes of land abandonment and production practices suited to the local context. In addition, a blueprint for a *territorial lab* in Monti Prenestini was developed. These tools provide a scientific and operational basis for future experimentation and spatial planning.

Through a reinterpretation of the phenomenon of natural reforestation that accompanies the abandonment of arid prairies⁵ in Monti Prenestini – often perceived as a threat – the project demonstrated how this phenomenon can become an opportunity to reshape and diversify the identity of the landscape, creating complementary economies to the pastoral tradition and opening up new perspectives in an area seeking to reinvent itself. In Monti Prenestini, a

¹ Lewin, Kurt. "Action Research and Minority Problems." *Journal of Social Issues* 2 (1946): 34-46.

² The *territorial lab* is an applied research tool conceived during this *Challenge*, halfway between *Living Labs* and *Land-Based Labs*. It is a place dedicated to experimentation geared toward landscape stewardship and regeneration of depopulated areas, with the aim of bringing out new forms of social innovation and stimulating the economic and social fabric. Solving concrete problems in a participatory way through innovative approaches makes new potentials tangible and motivates the investments needed to initiate larger-scale transformations.

³ *Living Labs* are user-centered open innovation environments currently supported by European policies, where citizens, public agencies, businesses and research centers co-develop solutions in real-world settings, promoting social and technological innovation through participatory processes.

⁴ *Land-Based Labs* are laboratories generally located in rural or natural settings—such as forests, agricultural landscapes, urban voids, and complex spatial environments—that conduct 1:1 scale experiments over long time horizons, with the goal of generating knowledge and doing applied research in the fields of landscape architecture, agriculture, and forestry.

⁵ Ecosystems characterized by herbaceous vegetation with few trees, typical of climates with limited rainfall.

territory characterized by low population density, uncertainties about agrarian generational turnover and land fragmentation, the *territorial lab* has emerged as a tool to catalyze systemic change. This is not an intervention with marginal implications, but an initiative capable of activating economic and social relationships along the entire supply chain, involving producers, processors and other key players. The project lays the foundations for regenerative processes that redefine the relationship between community, landscape and local economies. It offers a replicable model for territories facing similar challenges and an opportunity to overcome the limited role given to marginal territories as a consequence of the social changes of the twentieth century.

2.1

Challenge Results

Transitioning a Landscape has enabled the development of a well-structured project that offers Liminal, the initiative's *partners*, and the local actors involved a concrete starting point for experiments aimed at reinventing arid prairie management in Monti Prenestini. Through the *territorial lab* approach, the project proposed innovative solutions to address the challenges posed by land abandonment and natural reforestation, with a focus on creating incentives capable of harmonizing the ecological, cultural and economic needs of the area. The project proposal was based on an integrated research process that combined scientific analysis, advanced technologies, field experimentation and community involvement. This approach demonstrated how it is possible to respond practically and creatively to the complex challenges of marginal territories at risk of depopulation by proposing feasible strategies aligned with local priorities.

The research conducted as part of *Transitioning a Landscape* produced concrete and quantifiable results that underscored the depth and breadth of the project. Eighteen spatial maps were developed using GIS tools and satellite data, documenting key ecological, morphological and historical features. Twelve case studies from *Living Labs* and *Land-Based Labs* internationally were analyzed, accompanied by a literature review on two key themes: prairie abandonment and the concept of cultural landscapes. The research explored four funding opportunities to support *land-based lab* models in Monti Prenestini. Nine local actors were directly involved in the field and 63 stakeholders were identified for future collaborations. In addition, seven experimental observational exercises were conducted, including soil profiles and viewshed analyses. During an intensive workshop, strategic tools were developed, including tables to elucidate the causes of land abandonment, a SWOT analysis broken down into seven themes, lists of production practices akin to Monti Prenestini, and typological profiles of key actors along the food supply chain. Finally, the project led to the design of a two- to three-hectare *territorial lab*, complete with action plans, Gantt charts and links to European funding programs such as *A Soil Deal for Europe*, demonstrating an operational approach to finding new forms of sustainable management of arid prairies.

2.2

Contextual Overview

The phenomenon of agricultural land abandonment in Italy

The abandonment of agricultural land represents one of the most significant transformations that shaped Italy's rural territory in the 20th century, with profound repercussions at the landscape, ecological and socioeconomic levels. This phenomenon, rooted in structural changes in society and the economy, is a consequence of the difficulties that many territories faced in finding a sustainable economic function during Italy's modernization and industrialization, which made them less competitive due to their morphological characteristics. In a country historically tied to land management based on agro-sylvo-pastoral activities, the abandonment of land has meant the loss of an extraordinary diversity of cultural landscapes, along with the techniques and traditions that sustained them. For many territories, this loss has further compounded the difficulties of fitting into the tourism economy, a sector toward which governments are increasingly pointing as a development lever for inner areas⁶.

These changes raise urgent questions about how to restore a well-defined social role to the communities that inhabit these territories, especially against a European backdrop marked by a demographic winter that is hitting rural areas particularly hard. Although the cultural and technological transformations of the past fifty years have opened up new opportunities for rural economies, such as the production of high-value goods, ecosystem services, or other activities based on active land management, much remains to be understood about the governance processes and social dynamics needed to catalyze these innovative and sustainable models in the country's inner areas.

2.2.1 Causes of the Phenomenon

The reduction of agricultural activity in marginal territories is the result of a complex interweaving of social, morphological and economic dynamics that generate a negative feedback loop between them. The rural exodus, driven by the search for more secure and stable opportunities in urban centers, has progressively deprived these areas of the human capital needed to keep traditional agricultural practices alive. In areas already suffering from steep slopes and less productive soils, this loss has further compounded the inability to adopt technological innovations and competitive production models. Further complicating the picture, land fragmentation, a legacy of historical systems of property division, has not only hindered more integrated and rational land management, but has also generated recurrent conflicts between neighbors over inheritance, boundaries and the use of common infrastructure. These tensions have fueled distrust between actors, hampering attempts at collaboration.

⁶ Inner areas, according to the National Strategy for Inner Areas (SNAI), are territories significantly distant from essential services (education, health, mobility), often characterized by depopulation but with significant environmental and cultural resources.

This structural fragility has been further exacerbated by economic pressures that have penalized the traditional family farming activities that characterize places like Monti Prenestini. Profit margins in the conventional agribusiness sector have shrunk, while inadequate infrastructure and high operating costs have discouraged new investment. In addition, an increasingly complex bureaucratic apparatus rewards larger firms, making it difficult for these businesses to adapt to a changing environment. What was once a diverse economic fabric rooted in the territory today struggles to find space in a system that favors centralized and highly structured models.

2.2.2 Spatial Implications

The spatial impact of agricultural abandonment is complex and layered. The cessation of traditional agricultural practices has encouraged natural reforestation, with an enormous expansion of forests nationwide, which has occurred, however, at the expense of open habitats such as the arid prairies of Monti Prenestini, essential for biodiversity. This phenomenon, while bringing some ecological benefits, has altered previous balances, putting at risk animal and plant species that have thrived in landscapes shaped by centuries of human interaction. The shift to a more homogeneous landscape has reduced the variety of habitats developed through traditional management systems, depleting ecological resilience and the ability of the Italian territory to cope with future climate scenarios. In parallel, land abandonment has led to the loss of traditional agricultural infrastructure, such as terracing and water management systems, which regulated natural resources and preserved hydrogeological stability in areas with significant slopes.

As productive activities have declined, many rural communities have found themselves increasingly isolated, forced to rely on uncompetitive models such as commuting to urban centers or relying on a fragile and underdeveloped tourism sector. The lack of economic opportunities has triggered a vicious cycle of depopulation and decline in essential services, further undermining the vitality of these areas.

2.2.3 Land Abandonment in Monti Prenestini

In Monti Prenestini, the abandonment of traditional agricultural practices has transformed a landscape historically dominated by arid prairies, a habitat of great ecological value shaped by centuries of pastoral activity, adapted to severe environmental conditions such as steep slopes, high altitudes, rocky soils and windy conditions. Abandonment has resulted in a gradual reduction of grasslands, replaced by natural reforestation processes. This ecological succession begins with the encroachment of shrubs and perennial grass species unattractive to livestock, which lead to dense shrublands and, finally, young forests that now dominate the landscape.

Dry grasslands are recognized as priority habitats by the Habitats Directive, which establishes their protection criteria within the Natura 2000 network. At Monte Guadagnolo, a Special Conservation Area (SAC) in the highest elevations of Monti Prenestini protects the biodiversity of this habitat, safeguarding the animal and plant species associated with it. In recent decades, however, agro-pastoral activity has recorded a sharp decline, with a gradual shift from sheep to cattle pasturing. The remaining open areas are

Fig. 1

Detail of cartographies produced to study the history of the arid prairies in Monti Prenestini through aerial and satellite photographs. From left to right, the years 1945, 1954, 1984, 1994, 2024. This detail shows an area near Guadagnolo where, despite some degree of remaining grazing activity, the acceleration of forest advancement is clear.

mainly managed by a few families who continue to practice traditional management, often integrating agrotourism models to ensure the economic sustainability of the farms. However, the development of new agricultural entrepreneurship among young people remains a limited phenomenon. In addition, land that has already been reforested is now difficult to recover for use as pasture, not only because of the lack of incentives and high costs of intervention, but also because of current regulatory frameworks. This situation makes the ecological conservation of arid prairies particularly complex, the maintenance of which is generally dependent on the continuity of agro-pastoral activity.

2.2.4 The Role of Territorial Labs

Addressing the phenomenon of land abandonment requires an integrated approach to land management that balances ecological needs, the protection of historical and cultural resources, and the need for new economic incentives for rural communities. Without a strategy that holds them together, it will be difficult to find lasting solutions. This implies revaluing disappearing products, traditions and practices that give a strong identity to the territory, but also accepting and managing the ecological changes that have occurred, such as reforestation, and integrating them into new economies. It is also essential to rethink land tenure patterns, business structures and forms of collaboration among local actors, adapting them to current social and economic conditions. The goal must be to maintain the principle of active management that has historically characterized these territories, while transforming management models to ensure competitive and attractive opportunities that incentivize new generations to actively participate. It is important to consider that without the continuity of sustainable forms of landscape stewardship, it is difficult to imagine a lasting impact of complementary economic engines such as tourism in marginal territories.

Fig. 2

Three of the seven 1:15,000-scale maps produced during the Challenge to show different aspects that influence the state of arid prairies in Monti Prenestini. From left to right, these represent: plat map, slope class, and land use.

Living Lab and *Land-Based Lab* models represent a promising starting point for exploring this potential, especially in territories where the prospects may seem daunting. These are spaces of co-creation where diverse actors – farmers, researchers, administrators and citizens – collaborate to develop and test innovative solutions in real-world settings. Applied to the land, they allow targeted actions to be implemented on experimental plots, fostering research into new models of management and protection. These experiments on the ground offer a concrete opportunity to test hypotheses and catalyze interest. Through targeted pilot projects, it is possible not only to explore new practices and economies compatible with local development goals, but also to make opportunities tangible for those who want to remain connected to the territory.

The *Living Lab* approach not only responds to the complex issues of land abandonment, but is also strongly supported at the European level. The mission *A Soil Deal for Europe*⁷ aims to create 100 *Living Labs* and *Lighthouses*⁸ by 2030 to promote innovative land management practices. For this reason, they represent a concrete opportunity to access European

⁷ *A Soil Deal for Europe* is an EU mission to regenerate soil health by 2030 through local experiments and sustainable practices.

⁸ *Lighthouses* are exemplary cases, located in real-world settings, that show effective practices for soil management and regeneration, serving as a reference for other areas.

resources, knowledge and funding, complementing the territorial regeneration efforts already underway in the Monti Prenestini.⁹

2.3

Methodological Approach

The Transitioning a Landscape project adopted a multi-step methodological approach with the goal of gaining a detailed understanding of the drivers of arid prairie abandonment in Monti Prenestini. This approach aimed to design how an applied experimentation model (*territorial lab*) could integrate innovative and traditional practices to regenerate the landscape and contribute to local development.

2.3.1 Phase 1: Preliminary Research

The first phase focused on the collection and analysis of theoretical and contextual data to define the parameters of the project and deepen knowledge of the area.

1. **Mapping**

Creation of spatial maps using GIS tools and satellite data to identify morphological, climatic and historical features of the area, highlighting ecological gradients, temporal evolution of habitats and areas of special interest.

2. **Case Studies of *Land-Based Labs* and *Living Labs***

Development of case studies of *Land-Based Labs* and *Living Labs* internationally. Existing labs were profiled, analyzing their habitat, academic output, community involvement and longevity, with comparative tables to identify criteria relevant to Monti Prenestini.

3. **Contextual Analysis**

Broad assessment of the climatic, morphological, economic and historical characteristics of the area to understand its peculiarities and potential.

4. **Literature Review**

Deepening the team's understanding of scientific literature on grassland abandonment processes, as well as the cultural landscape concept, to integrate ecological and cultural criteria into the framework.

5. **Assessment of Financial Opportunities**

Exploration of existing local, national and European incentive mechanisms to support *territorial lab* models in Monti Prenestini.

⁹ Three public strategies for territorial regeneration currently converge in Monti Prenestini: the project financed by the Ministry of Culture's Bango Borghi grant (of which this research is a part), the Terre di Pre.Gio Inner Area under the SNAI, and the new programming of the Castelli Romani e Monti Prenestini LAG.

Fig. 3 (previous page)

One of the field exercises, in which the distribution of plant species was observed in small segments of arid prairies characterized by different levels of management.

2.3.2 Phase 2: Stakeholder Engagement and Field Observations

The operational phase integrated scientific knowledge, local input and operational tools into a cohesive framework on the factors that condition arid prairie abandonment, providing a concrete basis for future research and experimentation in Monti Prenestini.

1. Involvement of Actors

Through interviews and bilateral meetings, qualitative information was collected on the perceptions and priorities of local stakeholders in relation to arid prairie protection (farmers, ranchers, agrotourists, conservationists, educators, and other key players). Input was also gathered from outside experts, such as researchers conducting *Land-Based Labs* and culinary journalists. This process not only allowed technical analyses to be validated with local knowledge, but also promoted constructive dialogue between groups with different interests. Through this approach, a more relevant project strategy was achieved.

2. Field Observations

Broad qualitative and quantitative analyses in distinct areas representative of the local landscape were conducted. Soil profiles, vegetation transects, and scenic view identifications were conducted, integrating aerial drone surveys and direct observations along the same transects to observe ecological and abandonment gradients from different viewpoints. The observations proved useful in validating both the themes that emerged during discussions with stakeholders and the information represented in the large-scale maps.

2.3.3 Phase 3: Fieldwork Roundtable (Charrette)

An intensive workshop synthesized the data collected and led to the formulation of key tools and strategies to test new models for managing arid prairies in the process of abandonment.

1. Classification of the Causes of Abandonment

Creation of tables distinguishing causes by morphological, social and economic dimensions.

2. SWOT Analysis

Identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats for the future stewardship of arid prairies in Monti Prenestini.

3. List of Productive Practices

Study of possible agricultural and forestry practices and associated by-products, categorized by complexity and experimental feasibility.

4. Stakeholder Profiles

Identification of types of key players in food transformation processes and their potential interactions in a *territorial lab* model.

5. Territorial Lab Design

Planning of a 2-3 hectare lab crossing the current ecological gradient of the abandoned grasslands (prairies, transitional zones, forests) to stimulate the demand for and use of agricultural products from the area.

6. Conception of *Shaping the Ground*

Development of guidelines and recommendations on how an additional Liminal Challenge in 2024 could test the first steps of the developed methodological approach, evaluating its effectiveness and identifying opportunities for improvement.

Fig. 4

Diagram illustrating the expected dynamics among the actors involved in the territorial lab model and their individual incentives.

2.3.4 Phase 4: Synthesis and Project Development

The final phase translated the outcomes of the working table into an operational proposal for a *territorial lab* in Monti Prenestini that articulates its motivation and potential impact.

1. Tabularization and Diagramming of Conclusions

Displaying of conclusions drawn from the research and the benefits of the project proposal for the various stakeholders.

2. Integrated Methodological Approach

Development of a cohesive approach that can be used to enhance and innovate different practices and products along ecological gradient zones.

3. Zonal action plans

Guidelines for experiments on specific habitats with adapted strategies.

Fig. 5
Extract of the project Gantt (see appendices for the full diagram).

4. Gantt Chart

Detailed Gantt to plan the start-up and experimentation of the *territorial lab*, starting from high-priority, low-complexity activities toward more ambitious projects.

5. Integration with European Initiatives

Linking the project with programs such as *A Soil Deal for Europe* to ensure potential for economic support and strategic alignment of the proposal.

2.4

Challenges and Limitations

The research conducted as part of *Transitioning a Landscape* revealed some limitations mainly related to the short time frame of the project. Although solid goals were outlined, further investigation could strengthen the research and effectiveness of the proposals in the implementation phase.

From a research perspective, the priority given to the agricultural sector, because of its historical value and active role in the local economy, has reduced the space to explore other land management practices, such as forestry, carbon markets, and regional natural infrastructure (ecosystem services). In addition, the limited analysis of climate change has left open crucial questions about the best practices for the future of the land, particularly with respect to phenomena perceived by stakeholders, such as increasing high temperature peaks, decreasing snowfall, and decreasing low temperature peaks.

On the local stakeholder engagement front, while exhaustive mapping of relevant actors was completed, the tight timeframe prevented in-depth interaction with some key groups, such as livestock farmers. Subsequent initiatives, such as *Shaping the Ground*, could provide an opportunity to continue interaction with this category of actors.

On the project proposal side, some operational issues remain to be further investigated. Involving actors similar in type to one another, such as farmers, may face difficulties due to the historical collaboration issues noted earlier. In addition, the land access mechanism for the *territorial lab* needs further reflection to ensure that it does not negatively impact participation at the local level. The project also presents an opportunity to test innovative solutions to land fragmentation, a crucial aspect of improving land competitiveness which should not be overlooked. Another open challenge concerns how to ensure that the lab, while geographically located in a specific area, is perceived as a shared resource by the different communities/municipalities of Monti Prenestini, an element that will be influenced to a large extent by the selected location.

Finally, the management complexity of the *land laboratory* raises additional questions. While the holistic approach taken is ideal for stimulating integrated thinking about the future of land management, it requires further consideration to ensure that practices less integrated into the current supply chain receive priority. This could facilitate the achievement of results over time, avoiding overlap with existing initiatives and promoting a complementary strategy. Prioritizing underexploited but high-potential products and practices remains essential to contribute meaningfully to the future of the land.

2.5

Conclusions

The Transitioning a Landscape initiative concluded that ongoing natural reforestation in Monti Prenestini should not be interpreted as a sign of decline nor as a threat to the area's cultural identity. On the contrary, it can represent an opportunity to reinterpret and diversify this identity, creating new economic possibilities complementary to the pastoral tradition. The reactivation of the territorial system passes through the rediscovery of niche products that are competitive and rooted in the territory – both traditional and novel – and from the construction of connections with external realities, which are essential to incentivize the adoption of updated agro-sylvo-pastoral practices. The proposed *territorial lab* focused on this objective, promoting collaborations along the entire production chain and fostering the creation of new opportunities in the agricultural sector. Each concrete action foreseen was also designed as an opportunity to strengthen these relationships within and beyond the territory. The project aims to enhance products linked to the different areas of the Monti Prenestini ecological gradient, strengthening the food and culinary identity of the area and laying the foundations for a more attractive destination, in line with the growing rural tourism trends promoted by local governments.

A central element of the project was the investigation of the potential of *territorial labs*, a founding premise of the research that was confirmed during the fieldwork. The analyses highlighted the need for projects capable of catalyzing new land management, offering concrete incentives and new opportunities for those wishing to take root in Monti Prenestini. The low population density, high average age of agricultural workers and uncertainties related to generational turnover make it imperative to have a model that does not limit itself to marginal improvements, but triggers radical change. The *territorial lab* can act as an engine to invent new development paths, integrating scientific, social and operational dimensions, and involving local communities in co-designing incentives for a new management model in Monti Prenestini.

3.1

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